

Development of an Intelligent Imaging System for Fruits Adulteration Detection

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Abstract-The surface temperature of the object can potentially be measured using thermal imaging. In this study, the thermal behavior of apple fruit kept in a refrigerator was examined. The environmental inside the imaging chamber was maintained in the acquisition environment to obtain high-quality thermal photos of the fruit. The temperature differential between the various fruit areas was determined by analyzing the thermal images. Over the course of the storage period, the temperature at the bruise boundary (Tbd) was greater than the temperature at the bruised core (TC). Furthermore, the damaged apple was predicted using an improved deep-learning model. From the 400 apples, 3500 thermal pictures were captured over duration of ten days. Ten percent were used for testing, ten percent were used for validation, and eighty percent were used for training. The model was able to obtain the accuracy of 99%

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in computer science, electronics, and imaging have significantly improved nondestructive testing and quality control in the agro-food sector. This development is especially noticeable in the combination of artificial intelligence (AI) with infrared thermal imaging (TI) methods. AI-based TI is a non-contact technique that has found widespread use in post-harvest fruit handling, food processing, and agriculture. It shows promise in identifying a variety of quality parameters.

Using conventional evaluation methods, numerous researchers examined the quality of apple fruit and found bruising [6–10]. However, it is difficult and expensive to use these approaches for the automatic classification of apple damage. Previous methods have major drawbacks when it comes to preparing the dataset for online prediction because obtaining photos is relied on external factors like lighting, environment temperature. [11]. Any object's surface temperature variation could be detected by thermal imaging. Converting infrared (IR) radiation to an appropriate temperature is known as thermography. Compared to other imaging methods, thermal imaging has the following benefits: it is rapid, non-invasive, reproducible, easy to use, and doesn't require external illumination. These features make this technique useful in a variety of fields, such as quality control in the food sector, civil engineering, aerospace, automotive, electrical, and electronics [12]. The implementation of thermographs to evaluate fruit quality has grown with the advancement of software and image collection techniques [13].

Thermal imaging of both healthy and bruised apples showed ambiguity and discrepancies [14]. First, if fruit is cooled or heated to a regulated temperature and the bruises appear at varying depths beneath the skin, they can be identified [15–17]. To produce high-quality thermal pictures, previous research has employed either constant temperature or relative humidity. For retail applications, especially those conducted online, it is a laborious and complex process [18, 19]. Using thermal imaging, it can be challenging to conceive a method that can quickly and easily detect fruit bruising and determine when it happens. In earlier research, the main purpose of machine vision algorithms was to track and identify both healthy and spoiled fruit. A novel method called machine vision makes use of computers to "sense" objects. Machine-assisted driving, product quality identification, health management, and classification in the industrial and food processing sectors are just a few of the many uses for it. Numerous algorithms, including K nearest neighbor (KNN), artificial neural networks (ANN), backpropagation neural networks (BPNN), principal component analysis (PCA), support vector machines (SVM), and convolution neural networks (CNN), have been developed in recent decades to assess fruit bruises.

Yet, artificial neural network-based deep learning typically yielded the best detection outcomes. To assess such a strategy, a large sample data set is needed. But collecting it to train the model is difficult. Depending on the degree of damage and preservation, fruit damage and external temperature variations may differ. To the best of the author's knowledge, no thermal imaging analysis of an apple kept in a

refrigerator was offered from this angle. Therefore, creating a simple thermal imaging system using an active thermography technology to generate accurate thermal images was the main objective of this study. The second objective was to differentiate between healthy and damaged apple fruit using a modified deep learning algorithm based on a small sample data set of thermal images. The third objective was to look into the effects of surface temperature dispersion of apple fruit.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The insulation chamber

The chamber is made of wood, which is a good insulator of heat, and does not allow the image to be influenced by thermal radiation from the surroundings. Its dimensions are $30\text{ cm} \times 30\text{ cm} \times 25\text{ cm}$ in length, breadth, and height respectively. The inner layer is further padded with thermocol to avoid the heat from within the chamber to escape into the environment. It is then coated with a layer of black paint, so that the image captured can be viewed in high quality due to the clear background the black colour offers. This black layer of paint also acts as a good thermal absorber, which gives the images an even better quality.

Fig.1. Insulation chamber

Fig.2. Sample images of thermal image

III. IMAGE ACQUISITION

For 8 days, images were taken every day at of each fruit using FLIR thermal camera at room temperature (Figure 1). Cameras and fruit surfaces were kept at a distance of 0.5 m. Temperature gradients between objects and the surrounding environment can be adjusted by regulating the air temperature. As a result of this method, bruises can be detected and recognized in more extreme environments without developing a specific condition. The temperature of each fruit was measured using obtained thermal images. FLIR research tool was used to identify the surface temperatures. The damaged area of the fruit appeared brighter than the rest of its surface.

The temperature of the bruised center (T_C), the boundary of the damaged area (T_{bd}), and the remaining healthy regions (T_H) were measured. Ten randomly selected locations in the healthy area were measured for temperature, and the mean of these readings was used to determine the real temperature, disregarding maximum and lowest values. The final temperature was determined by taking the average of the temperatures of three randomly chosen spots in the bruised core and boundary. The healthy region temperature (T_H) was subtracted from the bruising center temperature (T_C) and the bruise boundary

temperature (T_{bd}) to get the temperature difference between the two locations ($\Delta T(c)$) and bruise boundary (ΔT_B).

Figure 2 displays the various temperature zones of the fruit based on spot measurements and the thermal imaging. The following formula was used to analyze the temperature from the thermal images:

$$(\Delta T_B) = T_{bd} - T_H$$

$$(\Delta T_C) = T_C - T_H$$

Where, ΔT_B Temperature difference in the bruise boundary, °C., T_{bd} Temperature of bruise boundary, °C, T_H Healthy region temperature, °C, T_C Temperature of bruise center, °C, ΔT_C Temperature difference in the bruise center, °C.

Fig.3. Block diagram of proposed work

IV. ANALYSIS OF ALGORITHM

The potential of CNN in the food industry has long been recognized and the food industry is now ranked among the top industries. A Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet/CNN) is a Deep Learning method

that can take in an input image, give various elements and objects in the image importance (learnable weights and biases), and be able to distinguish between them. Comparatively speaking, a CNN requires substantially less pre-processing than other classification methods. CNNs can learn these filters/characteristics with adequate training, whereas in primitive approaches filters are hand-engineered.

Thermal Images of apple have been categorized into normal and defective categories using convolutional neural networks, a supervised learning technique. Supervised learning depends on the training data to create a new set of class. CNN extracts the needed information from images for training, in contrast to standard machine learning techniques that require human feature extraction from images. Using proposed CNN structure, image were evaluated for the affected and good regions. Figure 3 shows the developed CNN structure.

Convolutional neural networks outperform other neural networks when given inputs such as images, voice, or audio. There are three basic categories of layers in them: Convolutional layer, pooling layer and Fully connected (FC) layer. The Convolutional layer is the fundamental component of a CNN and is where the majority of processing takes place. It needs input data, a filter, and a feature map, among other things. Filters move across the image to produce the feature output. The outputs of a linear operation such as convolution are then passed through a nonlinear activation function. the most common nonlinear activation function used presently is the rectified linear unit (ReLU), which simply computes the function. Pooling layer is used to lessen complexity, increase effectiveness, and lower the risk of over fitting. Fully connected layers allow input images to be organized hierarchically by connecting neurons to activation units of the layer over them. The output feature maps of the final convolution or pooling layer is typically flattened, i.e., transformed into a one-dimensional (1D) array of numbers (or vector), and connected to one or more fully connected layers, also known as dense layers, in which every input is connected to every output by a learnable weight. FC layers often employ a SoftMax activation function to classify inputs appropriately, producing a probability ranging from 0 to 1.

Fig.4. FRUITNet CNN

In order to determine the defect in the apple fruits, the FRUITNet CNN architecture is designed with Tensor flow. The feature extraction and classification is done by FRUITNet. A convolutional 2D layer with 16 filters, a kernel of 3x3, the input size of the image is 300x300x3, and the activation as ReLU is the first layer of the architecture. Next, a max pooling layer that halves the image dimension is added, thus after this layer, the output is shortened to 150x150x3. By using the same process, 4 of these layers are

stacked together with each subsequent CNN adding with 16, 32, 64, and 128 in convolutional filters. Finally, the output of the CNN layers is flattened and fed into a fully connected layer, followed by a sigmoid layer for binary classification. To fit the model faster and with more precision, all trainable parameters were updated using the Adam optimizer. To avoid reaching local minima of the loss function while maintaining the learning rate at 0.001, a regulated gradient descent was employed. The loss function of choice was sparse categorical cross entropy. Lastly, the model's performance was evaluated using different batch sizes (32, 64, and 128) and Adam optimizers. The algorithms used in this research were created in Python 3.9 and run on an 11th generation Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-11,500 processor running at 2.70 GHz with 16 GB of RAM.

```
model.summary()
```

Model: "sequential_2"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_8 (Conv2D)	(None, 298, 298, 16)	448
max_pooling2d_8 (MaxPooling 2D)	(None, 149, 149, 16)	0
conv2d_9 (Conv2D)	(None, 147, 147, 32)	4640
max_pooling2d_9 (MaxPooling 2D)	(None, 73, 73, 32)	0
conv2d_10 (Conv2D)	(None, 71, 71, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_10 (MaxPooling 2D)	(None, 35, 35, 64)	0
conv2d_11 (Conv2D)	(None, 33, 33, 128)	73856
max_pooling2d_11 (MaxPooling 2D)	(None, 16, 16, 128)	0
flatten_2 (Flatten)	(None, 32768)	0
dense_4 (Dense)	(None, 512)	16777728
dense_5 (Dense)	(None, 1)	513

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Total params: 16,875,681
Trainable params: 16,875,681
Non-trainable params: 0
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Fig.5. CNN Summary

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Thermal image analysis

The thermal image analysis shows that the temperature of the bruised center (T_C) is, on average, 3 °C–4 °C lower than that of the bruise boundary (T_{bd}) on the subsequent days. Figure 5 shows the analysis of the thermal images. Figure shows that the damage center's temperature (T_C) rises with only minor fluctuations. Conversely, the temperature in the healthy region (T_H) rises gradually starting on the fifth day after fluctuating from the first to the fourth day. At the bruising border (T_{bd}), average temperatures was 25.3°C,

respectively. The bruising center (T_C) had 23.1°C for the average Temperature. The healthy temperature (T_H) was 27.1 °C at its average.

Fig.6. Temperature Analysis of thermal image

B. Deep learning model performance

Fig.7. Input data

The dataset contains about 4500 thermal images of apple in all condition. The data that we fetched from the camera is divided into three folders: train, validation, and test. In these folders, excluding test, the folders 'ok' and 'bruised' contain the images of each class. The images were rescaled, such that their pixel

values are normalised between 0 and 1 without affecting the image quality. This will make it easier to train the CNN.

For training the network, the hyperparameters play a major role in CNN's accuracy and the training time of the network. The hyperparameters of the traditional CNN model were modified to fit the current dataset. The weights and biases of each layer had been optimized.

Learning rate is an important hyperparameter that affects the efficiency of the model. The selection of the learning rate is necessary to minimize the loss function. The higher the learning rate, the network trains faster but increases the loss function. The lower learning rate results in slow training of the network. The Network is trained with 0.00005, 0.0001, 0.0005, and 0.001, where 0.001 shows the better result and is shown in Figure. So, the networks are trained with a 0.001 learning rate. Next batch size is specified, which denotes the number of samples that will be propagated through the network in the given time. The `batch_size` can vary depending on the training set. The larger the training dataset, the larger the batch size. The Network is trained with 10, 16, 32, 64 and 128, where 32 shows the better accuracy result and is shown in Figure. So, the networks are trained with 32 batch size increasing the convergence precision.

The model is tested by using the testcase dataset. The samples and the types of images acquired, and the results given by our CNN model will be discussed in this unit. The inferences are also discussed elaborately in the forthcoming sections.

C. Results

The already categorized and created test dataset is given as the input to the model and is predicted. The model is then used to predict the images either individually or as a plot of several images within the database.

Fig.8. Input samples

Fig.9. Output data

From the Image, it is inferred that the dataset is processed through the proposed CNN, the out is classified.

D. Discussion

Apples with mechanical damage were captured using the active thermography method. When fruit is refrigerated in sufficient Temperature and for a shorter period of time, the thermal imaging yield significant results. Even in intricate settings, the many parts of the fruit can be identified. Mango fruit quality parameters, including flaws, illnesses, damage, pests, and the detection of artificially ripened apples, have been categorized using machine learning and deep learning approaches in recent studies. Digital image datasets are preferred for analysis and classification in these investigations. The primary drawback of digital fruit photos is their inability to identify interior tissue deterioration and injury before damage-induced browning takes place. Detection and sizing of ripe apples fruit was successfully investigated using thermal imaging and different classifiers.

Recent research on the detection of bruises in guava, pineapple, jujubes, strawberries, pears, and other fruits have successfully employed a variety of thermal imaging techniques. They looked into the injured fruits' area-wise thermal behavior. These investigations have demonstrated the thermal imaging system's capability for evaluating quality in pressure mark detection. The study's thermal imaging analysis revealed that there was a significant temperature differential between the marginal and healthy areas than between the center and healthy areas. The temperature of the border areas was higher than that of the bruised center and healthy areas because of the tissue injury. The greater temperature differential is caused by the hit, which speeds up the decomposition of the fruit's edge tissue. Furthermore, the fruit begins to color after the four day and does so more quickly.

In order to obtain clear thermal images during the investigation, the thermal imaging camera must be held in a stable posture without swaying because of its higher sensitivity. The turntable's thermal impression is preserved over the cold storage period, increasing its endurance for temperature analysis. The study's findings, which include data from thermal analysis and CNN's evaluation of fruit quality. A promising instrument for researching the thermal behavior of various fruits is the active thermal imaging system that has been created. This method works better for online real-time fruit damage classification.

VI. CONCLUSION

The results can be verified by manual inspection of the base data. However, the presence of shadows, shaky images, and variations in temperature denoted by a similar colour can give a false result. Border objects can also go undetected. CNN is effective tool for detection of adulteration in food substances. Successful implementation of the application developed for checking for adulteration in many more food products can lead to the complete elimination of lab set-up that is being used today. Since the product is very cheap and usable in any personal computer, it can be provided to shop keepers or to the more informed customer to detect adulteration. The images used can be of very low resolution- 640x480 up to HQ images too. A single Thermal Camera can be enough to sustain various models, thus there is no need of any alternative and expensive image acquisition systems. This significantly affects the overall cost of the final product. It makes the application targetable to shopkeepers and consumers.

The accuracy of the algorithm on a large scale as presented above is 99%. For a non-contact method of food detection, this is a very good level of accuracy, compared to existing methods. Moreover, the loss is minimal and various algorithms can be implemented further to increase the efficiency of the CNN model.

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